

A1_PS2_10_2023

Optimization of Reactive Power Distribution Among Generating Units Connected to Network via Step-Up Transformers with Different Transmission Ratios

J. DRAGOSAVAC^{1*}, Ž. JANDA¹, J. PAVLOVIĆ¹, J. NIKOLIĆ², Z. SIMEUNOVIĆ²

¹Nikola Tesla Institute of Electrical Engineering, University of Belgrade

²Joint stock company „Elektroprivreda Srbije”, branch TE “Kostolac A“
Serbia

jasna.dragosavac@ieent.org

SUMMARY

After replacing aging or faulty equipment, thermal power plants encounter the need for simultaneous operation of new and old equipment. Following the replacement of the one step-up transformer in multi-machine power plant non-uniform distribution of reactive powers and generators' terminal voltages occurred due to different step-up transformer transmission ratio. Uneven distribution results in higher generator heating for the generator operating at a higher apparent power, non-uniform distribution of stators' voltages in p.u. that results in varying distances to the allowable voltage limits, reduced reactive reserves, etc.

In the process of allocating reactive powers among generators, the goal is to achieve a balanced distribution of apparent powers. This ensures uniform heating of the generators and avoids operating them close to their thermal and voltage limits, where zones of accelerated generator aging are identified. Minimizing the voltage difference at the generators' terminals ensures an even voltage stress and an equidistant operating point of the generator from voltage limits. The third criteria, maintaining the maximum reactive reserve during voltage increase and decrease at the connection point ensures best power system reactive support. These requirements include ensuring that the difference in the generators' terminal voltages is not too significant, that the generated reactive powers on the generators are similar, and that the generated reactive powers approach their permissible limits gradually. Due to the arbitrary nature of these requirements (not too significant, similar, gradually), it is difficult to formulate the problem mathematically. However, constrained optimization is focused on determining a feasible solution rather than an optimal one. Therefore, the problem of allocating reactive powers, as described above, is best addressed through constrained optimization. This method requires defining constraints, variables, and an objective function and then finding a feasible distribution that satisfies both the soft requirements and hard limits. This paper presents a series of calculations performed to analyze the optimal allocation of reactive powers among the generators using an optimization procedure with constraints. Several optimization methods can be used for computing optimization function minimum or maximum. Understanding these methods is crucial for selecting the most appropriate approach for the defined problem and correctly interpreting the usefulness of the obtained results. In paper the evolutionary method is chosen. Several optimization functions were tested. Desired optimal allocation is computed. The impact of the voltage at the connection point was taken into account for the selected optimization criterion. Calculations were performed, and the optimal tap position was selected. However, it has been shown that the evolutionary method's duration depends on the computational time limit, making it unsuitable for automatic allocation of reactive powers in real-time. Automatic allocation of reactive powers ensures even loading of generators. It also takes into account the available reactive reserve at the power plant buses to cover the dynamics of renewable sources. As the development of allocation algorithms becomes more complex, it will be necessary to combine off-line algorithms from the family of artificial intelligence algorithms to create fast adaptive on-line control algorithms.

KEYWORDS

reactive power allocation - step-up transformer - tap changer - evolutionary algorithm - power plant

INTRODUCTION

The role of thermal power plants in modern power systems is undergoing significant changes during the energy transition. The energy transition aims to shift from continuous operation with constant power output to providing on-demand support when solar and wind power supply less energy due to weather conditions, ultimately phasing out coal-fired power plants. This energy crisis is altering the way thermal power plants are perceived.

Currently, they are recognized as reliable sources of flexibility in power systems, with modified operational modes involving frequent start-ups, shutdowns, and partial loading [1]. Key technical guidelines for modern high-renewable transmission grids, aimed at minimizing the risk of instability, recommend the following:

- Minimizing reactive power (VAR) obtained from generators during normal transmission grid operation:
 - Utilizing the capacities available in shunt capacitors to the maximum before activating generator VARs.
 - Utilizing capacities available in shunt capacitors in the distribution system to the maximum before activating shunts connected to the transmission grid.
- Having fast dynamic reactive power (e.g., generator VAR and SVC/STATCOM) available as reserves for unforeseen situations, preventing load loss during voltage drops, and allowing time to provide maximum reactive support when needed.

Thermal power plants also face pressure to reduce production costs, energy loss costs, and environmental protection costs (CO₂ emissions). Therefore, effective equipment management becomes a crucial aspect of generator operation. Ensuring the proper allocation of reactive power among generators while taking into account the factors mentioned earlier plays a role in efficiently managing the equipment.

After replacing aging or faulty equipment, thermal power plants encounter the need for simultaneous operation of new and old equipment. Following the replacement of the generator 1 step-up transformer at the "Kostolac A" Thermal Power Plant (TE KO A), the transmission ratios of generators 1 and 2 in TE KO A differ. The generator 1 step-up transformer is equipped with a tap changer: 112 kV/10.5 kV, $\pm 4 \cdot 1.25\%$. The transmission ratio on the generator 2 step-up transformer is 121 kV/15.75 kV. Due to the different values of transmission ratios of the transformers, certain outcomes arise: in normal operating conditions, when the voltages at the generators' terminals are close in p.u. value, the reactive powers of the generators significantly differ. Generator A2 operates at a lower voltage and higher reactive power, while generator A1 operates at a higher voltage and lower reactive power. This uneven distribution results in higher generator heating for the generator operating at a higher apparent power, non-uniform distribution of stators' voltages in p.u. that results in varying distances to the allowable voltage limits, reduced reactive reserves, etc. To achieve an optimal allocation of reactive powers between generator 1 and 2 that ensures maximum reactive support and balanced operation, an algorithm for allocating reactive powers needs to be synthesized. This paper presents a series of calculations performed to analyze the optimal allocation of reactive powers among the generators using an optimization procedure with constraints. The impact of the voltage at the connection point was taken into account for the selected optimization criterion. It was found that the available reactive ranges of generators A1 and A2 can be separated for certain voltages at high voltage side so the most favorable step-up transformer transmission ratio for step-up A1 should be selected based on the voltage value at the connection point. Calculations were performed, and the optimal switch position was selected.

OPTIMAL ALLOCATION OF REACTIVE POWER AMONG ELECTRICALLY CLOSE GENERATORS CONNECTED TO THE GRID VIA STEP-UP TRANSFORMERS WITH DIFFERENT TRANSMISSION RATIOS

After installing the new step-up transformer, operators at TE KO A allocated reactive powers and voltages according Figure 1. After a few days of operation, the reference voltage value on the automatic

voltage regulator of generator 2 was adjusted to reduce the generated reactive power of unit 2. The rated parameters of the generators and step-up transformers are provided in Table I, while the selected operating points are presented in Table II.

The typical allocation of real P_g and reactive power Q_g and voltage at generators' terminals V_g in multi-machine power plant in the winter period is as follows: $P_{gA1}=0.83$ pu, $Q_{gA1}=0.11$ pu, $S_{gA1}=0.68$ pu, $V_{gA1}=1.01$ pu, $P_{gA2}=1.00$ pu, $Q_{gA2}=0.28$ pu, $S_{gA2}=0.89$ pu, $V_{gA2}=0.97$ pu, and voltage at high side of transformer $V_{HV}=0.95$ pu. The result of this selected operating point is that the voltage at generator A1 is 4% higher than the voltage at generator A2, with the reactive power load in relation to the available reactive range being $KQ_{opt_A1}=17\%$ and $KQ_{opt_A2}=43\%$. The temperatures of generator A2 are 10 °C to 25 °C higher than those of A1, with all temperatures well within the permissible range.

Figure 1 Responses of reactive power, voltage, active and apparent power of generators 1 and 2 in TE KO A at the initially selected transmission ratio corresponding to position 3

Table 1 The rated parameters of the generators and step-up transformers

Generator	S_{g_Gen} [MVA]	P_{g_Gen} [MW]	V_{g_Gen} [kV]	Transformation ratio [kV/kV]	Tap positions	S_{g_Trans} [MVA]
TE KO A1	137.5	100	10.5	112/10.5	$\pm 4 * 1.25\%$	132
TE KO A2	235.5	210	15.75	121/15.75	/	250

Table 2 The selected „optimal“ operating points for tap changer position $k=3$

Generator	P_{g_Gen} [p.u.]	Q_{g_Gen} [Mvar]	$Q_{g_Gen}^{MAX}$ [Mvar]	$Q_{g_Gen}^{MIN}$ [Mvar]	S_{g_Gen} [p.u.]	V_{g_Gen} [p.u.]	$V_{HighVolt}$ [kV]	$T_{CuStatorGen}$ [°C]	$T_{FeStatorGe}$ [°C]	$T_{HydrogenGen}$ [°C]
TE KO A1	0.83	14.9	89.3	0	0.68	1.01	114.97	46	60	44
TE KO A2	1.00	66.3	122.7	27.1	0.89	0.97	114.97	71.5	46°C	53

Considering the altered nature of the power system with an increased percentage of variable sources, it's crucial to carefully consider various factors when determining generator operating points. These factors include operation at different real power levels, overall block efficiency, reactive power reserves, voltage reserves, remaining equipment lifetime, and more. This paper presents a systematic approach to identify criteria for selecting the most suitable generator operating points.

Optimization with constraints

In the process of allocating reactive powers among generators, the goal is to achieve a balanced distribution of apparent powers. This ensures uniform heating of the generators and avoids operating them close to their thermal and voltage limits, as defined in [2], where zones of accelerated generator aging are identified. This approach is also beneficial for the transmission grid, as it requires maximum reactive power changes during network disturbances, providing a significant reactive margin. Therefore, optimization must adhere to firm constraints:

$$0 < S_g < 1 \text{ p.u.} \quad (1)$$

$$0.95 < V_g < 1,05 \text{ p.u.} \quad (2)$$

$$Q_{SETPOINT} = Q_{g1} + Q_{g2} \quad (3)$$

$$Q_{gMIN} = f(Q_{gMIN} \text{ according P-Q diagram}, P_g, V_{110 \text{ kV}}) \quad (4)$$

$$Q_{gMAX} = f(Q_{gMAX} \text{ according P-Q diagram}, P_g, V_{110 \text{ kV}}) \quad (5)$$

$$Q_{gMIN} < Q_g < Q_{gMAX} \quad (6)$$

Optimization with constraints, also known as constrained optimization, involves optimizing an objective function with respect to decision variables while imposing restrictions on these variables. In such problems, the goal is to minimize or maximize an objective function while adhering to certain limitations. Constraints are essential to prevent the objective function from leading to undesirable operating points. The location of the optimum in nonlinear functions (maximum or minimum values) can occur at boundaries, between, or outside them. On the other hand, in linear functions, maximum or minimum values occur solely at boundaries, as depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Optimization with constraints: a) and b) nonlinear function and its optima, c) linear function and its optima

The general formulation of a constrained minimization problem is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min f(x) \quad (7) \\ & \exists g_i(x) = c_i \text{ za } i = 1, \dots, n \text{ (equality - type constraints)} \\ & \exists h_j(x) \geq d_j \text{ za } j = 1, \dots, m \text{ (inequality - type constraints)} \end{aligned}$$

where x is a vector of decision variables; $f(x)$ is the objective function to be optimized; $g_i(x)=c_i$ for $i=1, \dots, n$ and $h_j(x)=d_j$ for $j=1, \dots, m$ are the constraints that should be satisfied.

Allocating reactive powers in this case poses challenges due to conflicting conditions:

$$\Delta V_g = V_{g1} - V_{g2} \leq \Delta V_{g_MAX} \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta S_g = S_{g1} - S_{g2} \leq \Delta S_{g_MAX} \quad (9)$$

Minimizing the voltage difference at the generators' terminals (ΔV_g) directly affects the increase in ΔS_g . The first condition ensures an even voltage stress and an equidistant operating point of the generator from voltage limits. The second condition ensures uniform heating of the generator. The third condition is related to maintaining the maximum reactive reserve during voltage increase and decrease at the connection point:

$$\Delta Q_{rezeve_MAX} = f(Q_{g1MAX}, Q_{g2MAX}, Q_{g1MIN}, Q_{g2MIN}, V_{110\text{ kV}}, V_{g1MAX}, V_{g2MAX}, V_{g1MIN}, V_{g2MIN}) \quad (10)$$

In this case, in addition to limitations (1), (2), (3), (4) and (5), limitations defined by (8) and (9) were added.

Various methods exist for constrained optimization, depending on the objective function and constraints. While penalty methods can reduce constrained optimization problems to unconstrained ones, they may lead to convergence issues [4]. Thus, dedicated constrained optimization methods are sought. Linear programming, applicable when both the objective function and constraints are linear, is unsuitable for this scenario due to the nonlinear nature of the objective function. As an alternative, the Generalized Reduced Gradient (GRG) method observes the gradient or slope of the objective function as input values (or decision variables) change, aiming to identify the optimal solution when partial derivatives equal zero. However, like most classical nonlinear optimization algorithms, GRG can only find locally optimal solutions. When used for constraints optimization (8), (9), and (10) with the application of a penalty function, it fails to achieve the desired allocation shown in Figure 1. As a result, other constrained optimization methods are considered.

In computational intelligence (CI), the Evolutionary Algorithm (EA) falls under evolutionary computation [4]. Understanding the capabilities and limitations of evolutionary methods is crucial. In the best-case scenario, the evolutionary method, similar to other genetic or evolutionary algorithms, can find good solutions for relatively well-scaled models. However, as it does not rely on derivative or gradient information, it cannot determine if a given solution is optimal, leading to uncertainty about when to stop [5]. The evolutionary method only recognizes that a new candidate solution is "better" than previously found solutions. Consequently, it stops and returns a solution when heuristic rules (discussed below) indicate limited chances of further progress or when the time or effort limit is exceeded. Moreover, the evolutionary method's duration depends on the computational time limit, making it unsuitable for real-time management or automatic allocation of reactive powers in real-time.

Understanding these methods is crucial for selecting the most appropriate approach for the defined problem and correctly interpreting the usefulness of the obtained results.

DETERMINING THE DESIRED ALLOCATION OF REACTIVE POWERS USING AN EVOLUTIONARY METHOD AND DIFFERENT OPTIMIZATION OBJECTIVES

By applying the evolutionary computation to optimization functions such as (8), (9), and (10), we obtained distributions of reactive powers between generators 1 and 2 for the total power plant reactive power setpoint (Q_{SET_POINT}) set by the transmission network dispatcher. The results are presented in Figure 3.

In Figure 3 it is showed that the desired allocation defined in Table II ($Q_{SET_POINT} = 80$ Mvar, $Q_{gA1}=16$ Mvar, $Q_{gA2}=64$ Mvar, $V_{g1}=1.01$ p.u., and $V_{gA2}=0.97$ p.u.) was achieved with optimization based on criterion (10) (indicated by traces marked with a circle symbol). Traces marked with a square symbol represent optimization based on criterion (8) that minimizes the voltage difference at the ends of the generators, while traces marked with an asterisk symbol represent optimization based on criterion (9) that balances generator heating. Stricter boundary conditions in (8) (i.e., allowing smaller voltage differences) lead to a broader apparent power constraint to ensure convergence, and vice versa.

VALIDATION OPTIMIZATION TECHNIQUE FOR DIFFERENT VOLTAGES AT POINT OF COMMON COUPLING

After selecting criterion (10) as the most preferable for optimization, the next step was to test the robustness of the optimization under different voltages at point of common coupling. The results are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3 Determining the desired allocation of reactive powers using the evolutionary method and various optimization objective functions

Figure 4 The optimization procedure's validation is carried out for various voltages at the point of common coupling and tap position 3, Q_{gi} generated reactive power of unit i , $Q_{gi_MAX/MIN}$ maximum / minimum permitted reactive power of unit i

Figure 4 illustrates the varying available reactive ranges of the generators in response to fluctuations in the voltage at the point of common coupling. As a result, the available reactive reserve at the power plant

buses also varies accordingly. Additionally, the required voltage levels at the generators' terminals to achieve Q_{SET_POINT} depend on the voltage at the connection point. The selected transformer tap position $k=3$ provides the maximum reactive reserve when the grid voltage is at its lowest, i.e., 0.92 p.u. or 111.32 kV. For grid voltages of 0.97 p.u. or 117.37 kV, the reactive ranges of generators 1 and 2 are completely separated, the voltages are high, and the generators reach their limits. Thus, for higher grid voltages, adjusting the tap setting is necessary.

It should be noted that the calculations did not include modeling the network to which the power plant is connected; instead, it was modeled as an ideal voltage source. In reality, the Thevenin equivalent of the network has its own impedance, making the network "softer," and the level of generated reactive power affects the voltage at the high-voltage buses, which, in turn, impacts the constraints on the generator.

DETERMINATION OF THE OPTIMAL TRANSFORMER TAP SETTING USING CONSTRAINED OPTIMIZATION

In the final step, the optimal transformer tap setting was determined by executing the evolutionary algorithm for the most commonly expected grid voltage of 0.95 p.u. or 114.5 kV, considering tap positions $k=1, k=3, k=5,$ and $k=-1.4$. The last setting corresponds to both generators having the same transformer tap ratio of 121/Rated generator voltage and serves as a comparison. The calculation results are presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Determination of the optimal transformer tap setting using constrained optimization

Figure 5 reveals that an identical transformer tap ratio ensures equal voltage levels at the ends of the generators in relative units and provides maximum reactive reserve for both generators. It is evident that tap position $k=1$ results in the smallest voltage difference and the widest reactive range.

The distribution of reactive powers for different Q_{SET_POINT} shows a linear relationship within certain Q_{SET_POINT} ranges, when voltage constraints are not compromised, Figures 4 and 5. It also exhibits an asymptotic approach to the boundary constraints at the end of the segment, which is desirable. The distribution of reactive powers for tap position $k=1$ lacks a linear segment due to the characteristics of the applied evolutionary algorithm.

The transformer tap was tapped from position 3 to position 1, and the obtained results are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Responses of reactive power, voltage, active and apparent power of generators 1 and 2 in TE KO A at the optimally selected transmission ratio corresponding to position 1

In the next step, it is necessary to define clusters of voltage ranges at the connection point and the corresponding optimal transformer tap positions. Based on the results of the evolutionary algorithm, an adaptive control algorithm needs to be formulated for automatic allocation of reactive powers. The available range of reactive power for Q_{SET_POINT} will be divided into intervals, with linear dependencies for individual generators being defined within these intervals. These intervals and coefficients of linear dependencies will be subject to adaptation. This approach will achieve an acceptably suboptimal voltage distribution among the generators, with acceptable deviations in generator heating and maximal reactive reserve to support the stability of the power system.

CONCLUSION

The ongoing energy transition and energy crisis are reshaping the priorities and dynamics of thermal power plants' engagement. The role of conventional power plants will change somewhat in the future energy system. Management processes in thermal power plants will be designed to provide solid support to the system when renewable sources are unavailable due to resource unavailability. Under the new operating conditions, power plants will need to devise robust "asset management" systems. Automatic allocation of reactive powers ensures even loading of generators and transformer taps. It also takes into account the available reactive reserve at the power plant buses to cover the dynamics of renewable sources. As the development of allocation algorithms becomes more complex, it will be necessary to combine off-line algorithms from the family of artificial intelligence algorithms to create fast adaptive on-line control algorithms.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [1] Thermal power plants, Strom-Forschung, supported by Federal Ministry For Economic Affairs And Climate Action, available at <https://www.strom-forschung.de/research-topics/thermal-power-plants>
- [2] INTERNATIONAL STANDARD IEC 60034-1
- [3] Kurt Bryan and Yosi Shibberu, Penalty Functions and Constrained Optimization, available at <https://www.rose-hulman.edu/~bryan/lottamath/penalty.pdf>
- [4] Vikhar, P. A , "Evolutionary algorithms: A critical review and its future prospects". Proceedings of the 2016 International Conference on Global Trends in Signal Processing, Information Computing and Communication (ICGTSPICC). available at: 261–265. doi:10.1109/ICGTSPICC.2016.7955308. ISBN 978-1-5090-0467-6. S2CID 22100336
- [5] Wenyu Sun; Ya-Xiang Yuan (2010). Optimization Theory and Methods: Nonlinear Programming, Springer, ISBN 978-1441937650. p. 541
- [6] Excel Linear Programming, available at, <https://www.solver.com/>

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work was supported in part by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia under the Contract on the realization and financing of the scientific research work of Reseach and Innovation Organizations in 2023 (contract No. 451-03-47/2023-01/200038).